

“WHY CAN’T NATIONAL BECOME INTERNATIONAL?” (Fashion)

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Abstract: *Through this article, the writers analyze from a fashion point of view why local brands do not reach the international level. There are not many success stories of native companies in the fashion industry irrespective of the number of those already present. Based on such analysis, the authors identify several significant sources of this problem, including poor product quality, lack of manufacturing experience, design flaws, and lack of advertising funding. Surveying the Uzbek participants reveals that increasing product quality and design is the primary way for local companies to become more competitive. From the article the understanding is that a local firm needs to invest in high-quality materials, original designs, professional production, and good marketing strategies if it is to go global. These matters can help local companies increase their prospects of thrival in the international market and the longevity of the customer relationship.*

Key words: Fashion, national brand, international brand, clothing, quality, knowledge, advertisement, investment, design.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, many brands are being created around the world, innovations are being made, new ideas are being born on the world stage, new names, different styles are appearing. In the same way, there are many brands in Uzbekistan, but there are only a few well-known ones. Not all brands are as well-known as other international brands. But not all emerging brands could reach the global level. Ideas are more interesting than one another, but one idea alone cannot bring the brand to the international level. Similarly, there are many brands in Uzbekistan, but there are only a few well-known ones. Not all brands are as well-known as other international brands. Mainly in the clothing industry, there is currently no popular clothing brand produced in Uzbekistan. Why not? After all, all products exist, and our greatest wealth is our own. So, let's think about why exactly these ideas and brands are not suitable for people's choice? People are different and their opinions are different. Through this article, we tried to find out people's opinions by conducting research on this topic. What are their thoughts on this? A brief discussion

will be conducted about which factors can be the solution to this problem. Analyzing how close people's opinions are to the truth, we will also shed light on our findings. During our survey process, we encountered a variety of responses. We will discuss this below.

QUALITY OF MATERIALS

In terms of quality, national brand clothing does not meet international standards, and it avoids customers who pay attention to this aspect because of its material. The quality of the material is good, synthetic fibers are not used, but because it is made of 100% cotton, the duration of the clothes will be shortened, or on the contrary, the use of synthetic fibers may cause discomfort to human skin. Designed for limited wear, i.e. the garment cannot be worn many times, the material will become unusable if it is washed many times. Next problem is not making it strong, and the threads sticking out are not accurate, this is also a factor that lowers the quality level.

If we look at international brands, they have their target customers in some aspect. For example, the clothing brand Uniqlo is considered to be a brand for lovers of comfort and quality, the quality of which corresponds to world standards, and the durability of the clothes is also good.

KNOWLEDGE OF PRODUCTION

In the production process, of course, a certain level of knowledge is needed, which is in the process. It is in this process that due to the lack of knowledge and skills; some defects can be observed in the material and details of the clothes. It takes a certain level of knowledge and skills to make quality fabric from cotton, and we have cotton but no quality fabric, but it is exported to big countries, which are sent to China, Turkey, Russia and South Korea. (Uzbekistan, 2022). Those countries make cotton products for us and export them to us at a higher price. In our country, fabric is made of cotton, but due to the fact that it does not meet international requirements, even today, residents of Uzbekistan wear clothes from foreign countries and choose international clothes even in competitions. If we have enough knowledge in this process, then only quality fabric will be produced and we can come to the conclusion that the buyer who prefers quality more than any brand name will definitely choose Uzbek products.

DESIGN

Design plays an important role in every work, every beginning of work and business. And as we know most people have a problem with design. Since our topic is about clothing brand and clothing design problems that we face in many clothing stores that drag down the brand's reputation, here are some problems facing clothing design problems: development, finance, color scheme, material and equipment for handicraft.

Obviously, in business, especially in the clothing industry, there is a need for endless development as day by day there are more and more clothing designers.

People often fail to realize their ideas and skills due to financial problems in order to make quality and stylish designs. Many people think that it takes a lot of money to make clothes more stylish.

It's clear that, color matching design plays a huge role. In many designs, you can see non-designer work, such as too rough and banal designs and inappropriate colors that alienate a person from their brand.

Choosing quality and stylish fabrics is important for clothing designers because the choice of fabrics can ruin the style and design of the clothing. For example, designers use and make handicrafts (from beads, from threads, beads)

CUSTOMER TRUST & LOYALTY

Trust issues in the clothing brand industry can be varied, clients and customers of clothing designers can easily lose trust in the brand when faced with issues such as: quality, employee experience and competitors

The quality of the fabrics also plays a big role, with poor quality material people can lose trust in the brand, with sloppy work or handicraft the brand's reputation is reduced.

Inexperienced employees hold back the work, such as employees who cannot deal with customer requests and complaints. Employees who cannot find a common language, in the sales industry we often meet inexperienced employees or such as who do not get along with customers.

Competition is such a thing, if you do not constantly develop and do not make new and unique designs and styles, then competitors can bypass you, and the brand will remain untrend and lose customers of its brand.

ADVERTISMENT

Unfortunately, advertising is crucial for local fashion firms to reach the global market. They note that effective advertising makes customers loyal, increases customer trust, and ensures customer exposure. Thus, Uzbek companies have to advertise their superior value proposition – from quality to design – through TV and social networks, influencer collaborations, and ads.

Advertising has to reveal an interesting story of the brand's creation, the craftsmanship and the company's values. The increased promotion of local talent and products may be gained through international fashion events and communicating with trendy personalities that will help make connections with clients in other countries.

In other words, all national brands striving to sell their products overseas and build long-term relationships with customers need to invest in comprehensive and creative communications.

INVESTMENT

Of course, to implement any idea, to create a brand, owner need a certain amount of money, but to make it international, owner need both money and effort. To make it international, brand need advertising, good quality product, quality material for the product. It is in Uzbekistan that there are companies that produce quality clothes, but in terms of marketing, investment is needed. To

promote the brand, it is necessary to do quality advertising, not one, but several. And it goes back to investment. All brands attract customers through advertising. even if it is famous, brands invest a certain amount of money in order to innovate and not lose their customers. Nowadays, a good idea alone is not enough. For the brand to be a brand over the years, it was necessary to invest. For example, we can say that clothing brands such as Zara, Dior, which are well-known to all of us, invest in advertising, products, and growth in order to attract more customers and serve a wide range of customers, and this will definitely show the result and is showing.

PRIMARY RESEARCH

For primary research, we employed both, an online and offline survey. Our survey's primary goal was to identify the key distinctions between local and worldwide businesses and the obstacles that keep people from expanding internationally. We distributed our survey to Uzbek citizens. middle-aged individuals, students, and those aged 18 to 25. Over fifty individuals took part in our survey. We sought to determine and examine the areas in which the major local brands are now falling behind by using the study questions listed below. They are:

1. Your age? 2. Your gender? 3. Does a clothing brand play a role in your life? 4. How important is the brand's origin (local vs. international) to you when making a clothing purchase? 5. What factors would make you more likely to switch from an international brand to a local brand? 6. Do you think local brands have a harder time gaining trust and recognition compared to international brands? Why or why not? 7. Do you believe that local brands offer comparable quality to international brands at a lower price? 8. What factors do you consider when judging the price of a clothing item, beyond the brand name? 9. Would you be willing to pay more for a local brand if you believed in its quality and design? 10. Do you think local brands have a unique opportunity to connect with consumers on a more personal level through their values? 11. What are your overall thoughts on the fashion industry in your country?

An offline survey was conducted by interviewing Nodira Abdurakhmanova, the founder and creator of the COCO CHAPAN brand. We questioned them on the following:

1. Is it harder for local companies to become recognized and trusted than for global ones, in your opinion? Why is that? 2. Do you think local brands provide similar quality to those of foreign brands at a lesser cost? 3. When assessing garment prices, what other aspects do you take into account besides the brand name? 4. If the quality and design of a local brand was reliable, would you be prepared to pay extra for it? 5. Do local companies have a special chance to engage with customers personally through their values? 6. How do you generally feel about your nation's fashion industry? 7. In your opinion, what actions should local companies take to achieve global success? 8. How would you advise a regional apparel company attempting to enter a global market?

According to Nodira Abdurakhmanova, for local businesses could be challenging for them to become familiar and popular as foreign brands, which have less money and recognition.

Durability is often an issue still timely offer similar quality at relatively cheaper prices. While evaluating the price, consumers pay more attention to quality and strength of the material used, style and sustainable quality than focusing on brand recognition. People are absolutely ready to spend extra money if a local company proves that they can provide a dependable quality and design. There is an opportunity to directly communicate with customers through cultural authenticity and values, for local businesses. To be effective internationally they have to focus on design, marketing, quality enhancement, and web development. The strategies that can be employed in order to penetrate the foreign markets include better production, innovative products designs and excellent work integrated.

RESULT

For example, when asked *“What can increase the likelihood of switching to a local brand from an international brand?”*, 50% of people chose better quality, since international brands have the best quality, which meets people's demand, so in order to enter the international market, local brands are advised to improve the quality of the product. And the second reason is design, because the remaining 50%, half are not satisfied with the design, so improving the design can improve local brands.

Buying a brand between local and international for people has a small impact, about 65% of people. While 25% of people pay attention to the brand, people most important is the quality and design of the brand.

- When asked *“What steps do you think local brands need to take to achieve greater success internationally?”*, most people said to improve quality, because quality plays an important role in all areas of business, especially in the clothing industry, to justify the comparable prices for clothing, you need to improve the quality, as well as the design of clothing, clothing design sometimes does not match the norms of buyers, naturally everyone has their own taste, but collecting, learning the taste of each, you need to choose a design that suits everyone in order to improve the reputation of the brand and gain the trust of people so that they choose their local brand. Also, advertising and investment can attract the attention of customers, daily advertising can arouse people's interest in the brand, and development and investment will help the brand reach higher levels.

DISCUSSION

In this context, we find out that there are some imperatives that hinder Uzbek indigenous fashion firms from achieving competitiveness in foreign markets. The major problems include inefficient manufacturing processes, inadequate product design, inadequate marketing financing, and low customer confidence. As much as the nation has so many raw materials ranging from cotton, the local firms struggle to produce quality goods that will meet international standards. Secondly, most local firms may not afford efficient promotion and are unable to develop attractive and competitive designs.

From the response to our questionnaire, Uzbek consumers seem to value product quality and design far more than any associated logo and this means that local firms need to improve on other areas in order to design competitive brands. This ultimately means that most local brands cannot secure consumer trust, or even penetrate global markets without proper marketing, and consistent production of quality products.

Our research points to a severing of the native Uzbek brands' capability to compete internationally. While raw resources can be obtained in the country, there is inadequate physical facilities and expertise that would allow producers meet competition on the international market. Among all these pillars, two critical areas that need aggressive attention from local firms if they are to compete on the international platform are quality and design. Further, marketing expenses are required to gain customers' confidence at home and overseas markets and create brand consciousness.

These findings should draw the attention of local business people and government. According to the study, the most important factors that the entrepreneurs bring to focus in order to succeed in the international markets are quality, design, and marketing. What brands should do is invest in new designs, new goods and wiser advertisements. In this regard, the policymakers can offer the fashion sector infrastructure as well as training, which will in turn encourage domestic and export opportunities. This study has shown that global fashion brands may find new opportunities in making alliances with the emerging nations such as Uzbekistan that have the potential in providing fresh opportunities for new environmentally innovative sustainable fashion and unique textile production.

Most of the weaknesses are hence traceable to the fact that the study only targeted Uzbek customers, who may not necessarily possess the appropriate attitudes towards different foods as people in the rest of the world. Also, the internal business issues that might affect the globalization of local firms such as, cost of labor, or issues related to supply chain were not considered. In addition, the importance of the impact of factors aside from branding and product (influencer relations and brand storytelling) has not been explored sufficiently.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that not all brands can be international, but we have analyzed several factors above. Of course, we wrote this article based on surveys from people and our own research. It can also be added that when a brand becomes international and does not lose customers over time, when a brand can find a solution to a customer's problem, the goal is not to make more profit, but to solve a problem. Only then will the rest of the wishes come true. For example, Chanel was the first company to sell women's trousers, solving the problem of women, and this certainly served as a small factor for its popularity. If local Uzbek fashion businesses make investments in design, marketing, and quality, they can compete internationally. Despite the obstacles, local brands may thrive in the global market with smart efforts and focused investments. Deeper understanding of consumer behavior and optimal strategies for promoting locally made clothes globally may be obtained via more study.

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